

Synthesis and docking studies of novel quinoline substituted thiobarbituric acid derivatives as potential therapeutic agents for type-II diabetes

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Abstract : In the present work novel 5-((2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)methylene)-dihydro-2-thioxopyrimidine-4,6(1*H*,5*H*)-dione derivatives were synthesized by Knoevenagel condensation of 2-chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde with thiobarbituric acid. The synthesized compounds were successfully characterized by FTIR, ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR. Further comparative docking studies were carried out to find out the effective binding affinity of thiobarbituric acid derivatives with Peroxisome Proliferator Activated Receptor-Gamma (PPAR- γ) and aldose reductase receptors with to that of standard, Rosiglitazone and Epalrestat. The results obtained have clearly shown that 5-((2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)methylene)-dihydro-2-thioxopyrimidine-4,6(1*H*,5*H*)-dione possess good binding affinity with PPAR- γ , aldose reductase receptors on par with the standard.

Keywords : Thiobarbituric acid, quinoline, docking, type-II diabetes, Rosiglitazone.

Introduction

Barbituric acid derivatives have shown considerable attention in the field of medicine due to their potential pharmacological activity over the past few decades¹. Barbiturates, one of the most interesting derivatives of pyrimidines comprise an important valuable group of synthetic compounds particularly effective on central nervous system². Most of the well known drugs containing barbituric acid as a core moiety and act as sedatives, hypnotics, tranquilizers, anxiolytics and anticonvulsants³⁻⁷. Biological activities of barbituric acid derivatives were mainly determined by its relative hydrophilicity, hydrophobicity, electronic and steric effects. Compounds analogous to barbituric acid containing nitrogen and sulphur as electron donors have been shown to possess anticancer and antiviral activities⁸. In addition to CNS depressant activity barbiturates have been shown to other pharmacological activities which include herbicidal, immunomodulatory, antitubercular, insecticidal and PPAR- γ agonists⁹⁻¹². Quinoline represent an important class of *N*-heterocyclic compounds, occurs in several natural compounds and pharmacologically active substances displaying a broad range of biological activity^{13,14}.

In medicinal chemistry one of the major problem associated with barbituric acid include poor lipid solubility thereby preventing from penetrating the blood-brain bar-

rier. The lipid solubility of barbiturates can be increased by the replacement of oxygen at 2-position by sulphur (2-thiobarbituric acid). One of the better ways of making potential therapeutic agents is modification of C-5 position of thiobarbituric acid¹⁵. Replacement of hydrogen at C-5 position with active pharmacophoric groups gives maximum possibility of synthesizing numerous derivatives with wide biological applications. Literature search reveals only little amount of work has been published on the condensation reaction of thiobarbituric acids derivatives. Keeping in view of the affinity of thiobarbituric derivatives with PPAR- γ receptor and various biological activities of quinoline molecule we consider the thiobarbiturates as candidate scaffold for the design of novel therapeutic agents for type-II diabetes.

Experimental

Chemistry :

Solvents and reagents were commercially sourced and used without further purification. Thin layered chromatography (TLC) was performed on preparative plates of silica gel. Visualization was made with iodine chamber. Column chromatography was performed by using silica gel (100-200 mesh). Melting points were measured on Elchem Microprocessor based DT apparatus using an open capillary tube and are corrected with standard benzoic

acid. The NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Advance III – 400 MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal standard (chemical shifts δ in ppm).

The synthetic strategy leading to the key precursors **2**, **5** and the target compounds **6a-c** are illustrated in Fig. 3. The precursor **2** was prepared according to the method available in literature via Vilsmeier-Hack reaction of various substituted acetanilides, **1a-c** by using DMF and POCl₃. The precursor **3** was prepared from readily available starting materials thiourea, **3** and diethylmalonate, **4** by using sodium ethoxide as a catalyst in ethanol. The target 5-((2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)methylene)-dihydro-2-thioxopyrimidine-4,6(1*H*,5*H*)-dione, **6a-c** derivatives were prepared by Knoevenagel condensation of precursors **2** and **5** by using piperidine as a base catalyst. The mixture was kept under reflux for 6 h and completion of the reaction was monitored by thin layer chromatography using petroleum ether : ethylacetate solvent system.

Results and discussion

Knoevenagel condensation of 2-chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde with thiobarbituric acid was successfully carried out by using piperidine as a base catalyst. The 5-

((2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)methylene)-dihydro-2-thioxopyrimidine-4,6(1*H*,5*H*)-dione, **6a** as synthesized was confirmed using FT-IR, ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR. FT-IR spectra shows absorption peak at 1614.42 cm⁻¹ for the existence of amide CO-NH bond. The existence of free -C=O peak at 1687.71 cm⁻¹ shows the presence of carbonyl group, and the corresponding -NH stretching is observed in the region of 3061.03 cm⁻¹. ¹H NMR spectra of 5-((2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)methylene)-dihydro-2-thioxopyrimidine-4,6(1*H*,5*H*)-dione, **6a** shows eight protons in which the existence of NH peak was obtained at δ 6.026 and alkene CH in the range of δ 7.686 and ¹³C NMR spectra displays fifteen carbons in which the carbonyl group of thiobarbituric showed a peak at 160.36 ppm and the peak corresponding to C=S was obtained in the range of 190.84 respectively which confirms the formation of the compound.

The most stable docking structure of synthesized thiobarbituric acid derivatives complexed both with PPAR- γ receptor and aldose reductase receptor are shown in Fig. 1 which clearly indicate the synthesized ligands are having strong binding interactions with the receptor. The results (Table 1) obtained from the docking studies have

Fig. 1. (A) Docking of **6a** with the active site of PPAR- γ receptor. (B) Hydrophobic interaction of **6a** with aldose reductase.

Table 1. Docking studies and binding affinity of various ligands 6a-c and standard					
Ligand	Mol Dock Score [grid]	Mol Dock Score	Rerank Score	RMSD	Torsion
Rosiglitazone	-135.1782	-134.2014	-107.1421	97.1295	5
6a	-104.1240	-102.3225	-85.6940	79.1210	3
6b	-109.5271	-106.8219	-88.1224	89.0526	2
6c	-98.0467	-95.2517	-75.7807	71.3345	3
Epalrestat	-95.1387	-93.1482	-68.7120	67.1522	3
6a	-78.3219	-76.8841	-57.2318	54.2341	3
6b	-82.7188	-80.3265	-62.3695	63.1471	2
6c	-72.1963	-68.1195	-48.4123	45.3287	3

showed that of 5-((2-chloro-5-methoxy-quinolin-3-yl)methylene)-dihydro-2-thioxopyrimidine-4,6(1*H*,5*H*)-dione, **6b** have better binding affinity showing docking score of -102.12 kcal/mole, -93.14 kcal/mole with PPAR- γ and aldose reductase receptors which were in comparable to that of standards Rosiglitazone and Epalrestat. The hydrophobic, electrostatic and steric interactions of **6a** with surrounding amino acid residues of PPAR- γ receptor were shown in Fig. 2.

Docking studies :

The docking analysis of compounds **6a-c** and standards Rosiglitazone and Epalrestat were carried out by

Fig. 2. Various interactions of 6a derivative with amino acid residues of PPAR- γ receptor.

Fig. 3. Synthesis of novel target 5-((2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)methylene)-dihydro-2-thioxopyrimidine-4,6(1H,5H)-dione, 6a-c derivatives.

using Molegro Virtual Docker.v.4.0. The PPAR- γ receptor (ID-2Q8S) and aldose reductase (ID-1ABN) was taken from protein data bank. The derivatives of the final compounds were docked with the receptors and the interaction of ligands with the receptor were shown.

Conclusion

Novel synthesis of 5-((2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)methylene)-dihydro-2-thioxopyrimidine-4,6(1H,5H)-dione 6a-c derivatives have been reported and a comparison of versatile role of thiobarbituric acid nucleus for the treatment of type II diabetes have been evaluated. The molecular docking and binding affinities of both ligands as well as

standards with PPAR- γ and aldose reductase receptors has been explored. The oral anti-hyperglycemic drugs available in the market possess some toxic side effects, so in future more research has to be carried out to explore antidiabetic potential of novel thiobarbituric acid derivatives with minimum side effects.

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